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High-fidelity Electric Drivetrain Modeling and Control of a WaveBot Wave Energy Converter

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Abstract

The development of ocean wave energy conversion technologies is receiving growing interest, but many challenges need to be addressed to make Wave Energy Converters (WECs) economically viable. One crucial challenge is the inefficient conversion of mechanical and electrical power through the Power Take-Off (PTO) unit. The understanding of the losses in the PTO unit needs to be improved, as most of the literature focuses on developing advanced PTO controls or optimizing the hydrodynamics (mechanical power-oriented). This study proposes a high-fidelity wave-to-wire model of a WaveBot WEC that directly models the dynamic behavior of the power electronics and aims at accurately capturing the losses in the PTO unit. The hydrodynamic model is an empirical-based model, and the PTO unit is modeled in MATLAB/Simscape and includes a Permanent Magnetic Synchronous Motor (PMSM), a DC-to-AC Inverter, and a DC bus link. All the models of these components are calibrated according to the equipment that is used in hardware tank testing. A three-tiered control of the system is implemented, which includes the PTO control, the motor control, and the Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) scheme. Numerical simulations are first conducted to analyze the losses in the PTO unit. The results show both the DC voltage and the switching frequency are inversely proportional to the PTO efficiency, and the efficiency can be improved by 28.52% when the optimal DC voltage (minimum threshold that guarantees the control operations) and switching frequency (5 kHz) are selected. Moreover, it is also found that the DC voltage impacts both the inverter conduction loss and switch loss, while the switching frequency only influences the switching loss, and both factors have no impact on the motor loss. Finally, time domain simulations are conducted to further demonstrate the opportunity presented in loss analysis. Under optimal DC voltage and switching frequency, the DC power generation is improved by 56.02% under a small wave condition and 61.78% under an intermediate wave condition.

Keywords: Wave Energy Converter; Wave-to-Wire model; Control; Switching loss; Conduction loss

1. Introduction

Ocean wave energy has garnered significant attention in research. It offers reliability, predictability, and a high power density, making it a promising renewable energy source [1]. However, compared to solar and land-based wind energy, wave energy conversion technologies are still in their early stages of development. Over the past few decades, substantial efforts have been made to advance wave energy conversion technologies, including wave resource

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assessment [2 - 4], modeling of WEC hydrodynamics [5 - 7], and developing Power Take-Off (PTO) controls [8 - 10]. Despite these advancements, there are still many challenges that must be addressed toward commercial applications of WECs.

One crucial challenge is the inefficient conversion from mechanical to electrical power through the PTO unit. There is a need for a better understanding of losses in the PTO unit, as existing literature primarily emphasizes enhancing the mechanical power harvested rather than focusing on improving total power conversion efficiency. The effects of PTO losses (especially the power electronics) are often neglected. This results in a significantly degraded performance of WECs in electricity generation (e.g., as shown in [11]), even in cases where electrical power must be expended to maximize mechanical power, which is a significant concern. Limited studies in the literature investigated the performance, impacts, and control of power electronics in the PTO unit. Given the oscillation nature of wave power (unlike other renewable energy resources) which complicates the control design, a large volume of these studies concentrate on the development of controls for the power converters [12]. For instance, the effectiveness of linear PI control is demonstrated in references [13 - 17], which is later found may not be the best solution in all operating ranges (e.g., field-weakening region [18]) due to the nonlinear nature of the system [19]. Therefore, recently, several nonlinear controls are proposed. For example, A LiTe-Con control is applied to maximize the power production, and a Lyapunov-based nonlinear control is developed for the generator side converter in [20]. The effectiveness of the control framework is validated by a wave-to-grid model which considers the drive train both on the device side (e.g., linear generator, power converter) and on the grid side (e.g., DC bus, storage, power converter, and grid). The reference shows a significant improvement of the proposed control framework compared to the passive damping control in terms of wave-to-grid energy conversion efficiency. Moreover, reference [21] proposed a nonlinear back-stepping control for the generator side converter of an Oscillating Water Column (OWC) device. It is verified that the applied nonlinear control outperforms traditional Field-Oriented Control (FOC) in terms of wave power generation efficiency, system stability, and robustness.

Although there have been promising advancements in improving PTO efficiency, there are still drawbacks in these studies such as the inaccurate consideration of the losses in power converters which may potentially overestimate the efficiency of the PTO unit. Some studies [16,20] do not directly model the dynamic behavior of the power electronics in the power converter (e.g., averaged model), though computationally efficient this approach is not sufficient to capture losses. On the other hand, although the switching model is considered in the power converter in references [14,17,21], the losses of these power electronics are either significantly underestimated (negligible in [17]) or even not modeled [21]. The switching losses are more dedicatedly modeled in [22] according to the characteristics of a realistic insulated-gate bipolar transistor (IGBT) device. Practical data of the losses of the on and off events are incorporated, however, the conduction losses of these transistors are not considered. There is a strong need of modeling the losses in the power converters accurately according to practical devices such that to have a precise assessment of the system and control performance, evaluate the impacts of varied parameters, and benefit future control designs to improve efficiency.

In this paper, a high-fidelity wave-to-wire model of a WaveBot WEC, which directly models the dynamic behavior of the power electronics, and aims at accurately capturing the losses in the PTO unit is proposed. The overall wave-to-wire (W2W) model is developed in MATLAB/Simscape and encompasses the buoy hydrodynamics and the model of the drivetrain, which consists of a Permanent Magnetic Synchronous Motor (PMSM), a DC-to-AC Inverter, and a DC bus link. It is noted that all the parameters used in the model are identified according to the real equipment used in the hardware testing to guarantee the accuracy of the numerical model. Given that this study focuses on modeling, assessing, and analyzing the losses in the PTO unit, a baseline control framework is applied. The control framework is composed of three tiers which include the PTO control (Proportional-Integral (PI) control to maximize power harvesting), the motor control (Field-Oriented control (FOC) to regulate the electric machine mechanics), and the Pulse Width Modulation (Sinusoidal PWM to regulate the voltage supply). Finally, the losses considered in the PTO unit include the motor copper losses, the conduction losses, and the switching losses of the power electronics.

This study presents a high-fidelity wave-to-wire model of a WaveBot WEC, which accurately includes the losses in the power converters. This improved model not only shows that the losses in the power converters are not negligible but also enhances the understanding of how different parameters affect these losses. Several critical parameters (e.g., the DC bus voltage and the switching frequency) have been identified as worthy of consideration in future control development to further enhance PTO efficiency. This paper is organized as follows: the modeling and control are introduced in Section. 2, and the results are discussed in Section. 3. Finally, the conclusion is drawn in Section. 4.

2. Methodology

The configuration of the overall wave-to-wire model is presented in Fig. 1. As shown in the figure, the heave motion of the WaveBot will be translated to the rotational motion via a rack and pinion connection. This rotational motion will then drive the motion of the rotor of the PMSM to produce three-phase power. The three-phase power will be converted to the power on the DC bus via an AC/DC inverter which controls the AC voltage and regulates the torque provided by the electric machine. The modeling and control of the proposed system are introduced in detail in the following sections.

Figure 1: Schematic of the wave-to-wire configuration of WaveBot

2.1 Hydrodynamics

WaveBot, as shown in Fig. 1, is a point-absorber type WEC which is capable of harvesting wave power in heave, surge, and pitch [6], while only the heave mode is considered in this study. The WEC dynamics can be described by linear wave theory:

$$M\ddot{z} = F_e + F_s + F_r + F_v + F_{PTO} \quad (1)$$

where $M = M_r + M_\infty$ represents the total mass which is the summation of the rigid body mass and added mass at the infinity frequency, and z denotes the heave displacement. Furthermore, F_e is the excitation force which is the external force provided by ocean waves. F_s is the hydrostatic force, F_r is the radiation damping force that is induced by the motion of the buoy, and F_v represents the viscous drag. Finally, F_{PTO} is the actuation force provided by the PTO unit. The mechanical impedance of WaveBot can be calculated by converting Eq. (1) into frequency domain as:

$$M_r i\omega V(\omega) = F_e(\omega) + F_s(\omega) + F_r(\omega) + F_v(\omega) + F_{PTO}(\omega) \quad (2)$$

where $V(\omega)$ is the WEC velocity in frequency domain and:

$$\begin{aligned} F_s(\omega) &= -\frac{K}{i\omega} V(\omega) \\ F_r(\omega) &= -(B(\omega) + i\omega A(\omega))V(\omega) \\ F_v(\omega) &= -B_v V(\omega) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In (3), K and B_v represent the hydrostatic restoring coefficient and the viscous drag coefficient respectively. Moreover, $B(\omega)$ and $A(\omega)$ are the frequency-dependent radiation damping and added mass. Accordingly, the mechanical impedance can be computed as:

$$Z(\omega) = \frac{F_e(\omega) + F_{PTO}(\omega)}{V(\omega)} = B(\omega) + B_v + i(\omega(M_r + A(\omega)) - \frac{K}{\omega}) \quad (4)$$

In this research, an experimentally validated admittance model is utilized to model the hydrodynamics which is basically inverse of the impedance:

$$Y(\omega) = \frac{1}{Z(\omega)} \quad (5)$$

The frequency response of the identified admittance model is presented in Fig. 2, and according to [6], the model has a good agreement with the tank testing results.

Figure 2: Relationship between the input forces and output system response can be described by an admittance model.

Table 1. Motor specifications.

Description	Parameter	Value
Inductance 0-axis	L_0	0.1mH
Inductance d-axis	L_d	52mH
Inductance q-axis	L_q	52mH
Stator resistance	R_s	0.483Ohm
Torque constant	K_t	7.186
Permanent Magnet Flux	ψ_m	0.2994Wb
Number of pole pairs	n_p	24

Figure 3: Actual motor hardware

2.2 Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor

The linear motion of the WEC will be converted to the rotational motion via a rack and pinion system which drives the Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM), and the PMSM is controlled by the motor drive to provide the desired actuation force to the WEC:

$$\begin{aligned} F_{PTO} &= \frac{T_e}{r} \\ v &= r\omega_m \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where v is the linear heave velocity of the WEC, and ω_m is the mechanical rotational speed of the electrical machine. In addition, r is the gear radius of the rack and pinion, and T_e is the torque provided by the electrical machine. The PMSM produces three-phase voltage ($\overline{v}_{abc} = [v_a, v_b, v_c]^T$) and current ($\overline{i}_{abc} = [i_a, i_b, i_c]^T$). However, it is typically challenging to directly work in the ABC domain (time-varying system). Accordingly, the rotating reference frame approach is used where:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{v}_{dq0} &= [v_d, v_q, v_0]^T = \mathbf{T}\overline{v}_{abc} \\ \overline{i}_{dq0} &= [i_d, i_q, i_0]^T = \mathbf{T}\overline{i}_{abc} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

In this equation, \mathbf{T} is the Park transformation matrix. The resulting motor dynamics expressed in the dq0 frame can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} v_d &= R_s i_d + L_d \dot{i}_d - n_p \omega i_q L_q \\ v_q &= R_s i_q + L_q \dot{i}_q + n_p \omega (i_d L_d + \psi_m) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

In this equation, R_s is the equivalent resistance of the stator winding, L_d and L_q are the stator inductance in the d and q-axis respectively. In addition, n_p is the number of pole pairs, and ψ_m is the permanent magnet flux linkage. The resulting torque provided by the PMSM can be expressed as:

$$T_e = \frac{3}{2} n_p (i_q (i_d L_d + \psi_m) - i_d i_q L_q) \quad (9)$$

It is noted that the parameters of the PM machine are selected according to the actual motor (as shown in Fig. 3) applied in WaveBot: MF0310100-C0X, which is supplied by Allied Motion. The actual motor specifications are summarized in Table. 1.

2.3 Motor drive

In this study, the switching devices will be modeled explicitly by considering both switching losses and conduction losses. A standard three-phase two-level inverter is adopted as the motor drive with six IGBT devices. The switching mechanism of the IGBT is modeled as: when the gate-emitter voltage is higher than the threshold voltage, the switch is on; otherwise the switch is off:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{If } (v_{CE} > v_f) \ \&\& \ (G > v_{th}) \\
 & i_{CE} = \frac{v_{CE} - v_f(1 - R_{on}G_{off})}{R_{on}} \\
 & \text{else} \\
 & i_{CE} = v_{CE}G_{off} \\
 & \text{end}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

where i_{CE} and v_{CE} are the collector-emitter current and voltage respectively. G is the gate voltage, v_f is the forward voltage, and v_{th} is the threshold voltage. Moreover, R_{on} and G_{off} are the on-state resistance and off-state conductance respectively. The diode that is implemented in parallel with the IGBT is modeled by using a similar piecewise linear model. The parameters used in the IGBT and diode are summarized in Table. 2 and 3, respectively.

Table 2. IGBT parameters used in simulation.

Description	Parameter	Value
On-state Resistance	R_{on}	0.3Ohm
Off-state Conductance	G_{off}	$1 \times 10^{-8} 1/\text{Ohm}$
Threshold Voltage	v_{th}	0.6V
Forward Voltage	v_f	0.1V
Switch-on Loss	E_{on}	$91.44 \times 10^{-3} \text{J}$
Switch-off Loss	E_{off}	$68.56 \times 10^{-3} \text{J}$

Table 3. Diode parameters used in simulation.

Description	Parameter	Value
On-state Resistance	$R_{on,d}$	0.15Ohm
Off-state Conductance	$G_{off,d}$	$1 \times 10^{-8} 1/\text{Ohm}$
Forward Voltage	$v_{f,d}$	0.1V
Junction Capacitance	C_d	5pF

Both the conduction losses and switching losses are modelled. Which, the conduction loss of IGBTs and Diodes are computed by the product of the voltage and current across the device (e.g., between the collector and emitter for IGBTs). The switching (comulation) losses are physically caused by the on and off events of the devices .The energy consumption due to these events can be modelled as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{on} &= E_{on,0} \frac{v_{CE}}{v_{CE,nom}} \frac{i_{CE}}{i_{CE,nom}} \\
 E_{off} &= E_{off,0} \frac{v_{CE}}{v_{CE,nom}} \frac{i_{CE}}{i_{CE,nom}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where $E_{on,0}$ and $E_{off,0}$ are the switching losses measured at the reference values $v_{CE,nom}$ and $i_{CE,nom}$. The average switching power can be thus computed as:

$$P_{sw} = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{N_{on}} E_{on} + \sum_{n=1}^{N_{off}} E_{off}}{T_{sim}} \tag{12}$$

where N_{on} and N_{off} represent the total number of on and off switching events over the simulation horizon T_{sim} .

2.4 Controls

The control in this problem has three hierarchies including the hydrodynamics control, motor control, and Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) schemes. Each control has different objectives and is applied in different frequencies of

dynamics. Which, the hydrodynamics control is developed to maximize the mechanical power that can be harvested by the WEC. Given the relatively large period of ocean waves (typically ranging from 6s to 12s), this control is applied for low-frequency dynamics. In contrast, the motor control is applied in a higher frequency range which is designed to regulate the current such that the desired actuation force (computed from the hydrodynamics control) can be supplied. Finally, the three-phase reference voltage signal generated by the motor control will be supported by controlling the inverter with PWM schemes (usually greater than 5kHz). The hydrodynamics control is given as:

$$F_{PTO,ref} = -K_p z - K_d \dot{z} \quad (13)$$

where K_p and K_d are the proportional and derivative gains respectively. With regard to the motor control, a field-oriented control (FOC) is implemented. The optimal PTO force can be translated to the reference currents in the dq0 frame as:

$$\begin{aligned} i_{d,ref} &= 0 \\ i_{q,ref} &= T_{e,ref} \frac{2}{3n_p \psi_m} \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the reference motor torque can be computed as $T_{e,ref} = F_{PTO,ref} r$. A proportional-integral (PI) control is incorporated to regulate the errors between the actual dq frame currents and the reference:

$$\begin{aligned} v_{d,ref} &= K_{p,d}(i_d - i_{d,ref}) + K_{i,d} \int (i_d - i_{d,ref}) dt \\ v_{q,ref} &= K_{p,q}(i_q - i_{q,ref}) + K_{i,q} \int (i_q - i_{q,ref}) dt \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

In this equation, $K_{p,d}$, $K_{i,d}$, $K_{p,q}$, and $K_{i,q}$ are the proportional and integral gains in dq frames respectively. To support the desired three-phase voltage, a Sinusoidal PWM (SPWM) scheme is applied. In general, the reference voltage will be compared with a triangle carrier wave at certain sample points. The switch-on pulse will be generated if the reference is higher than the carrier; otherwise, a switch-off pulse will be generated. In this research, the natural sampling method is adopted in the PWM scheme, which takes samples whenever the reference signal intersects with the carrier signal.

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 4: Complete wave-to-wire model developed in Simulink and details of the subsystems.

The simulation results are presented and discussed in this section. The model described in Section. 2 is developed in MATLAB/Simulink as shown in Fig. 4. The simulations are conducted with a fixed-step solver with a time-step of

0.5×10^{-6} s. The simulations are run on a computer with an intel core i7 – 12700 2.10GHz processor, and 32 GB of RAM. The cost of a 30s numerical simulation is around 2.17Hrs for a small wave and 4.35Hrs for an intermediate wave. It is noted that given the amount of data generated from the simulation, most calculations are directly conducted online (e.g., the losses calculations) to prevent excessive memory usage if extensive amounts of data are stored.

3.1 Losses Analysis

Given that one of the main objectives of this research is to assess and understand the losses of the PTO unit, first the performance of the PTO unit is discussed. In this context, the PTO unit will be first isolated from the complete system, instead, it will be supplied by a constant velocity and controlled to support a constant motor torque. From the loss calculation introduced in Section. 2, the major factors that impact the loss performance are the DC voltage (v_{DC}), switching frequency (F_{sw}), as well as the motor speed and torque. Since the motor torque and speed are variables rather than parameters, the impacts of the DC voltage and the switching frequency will be discussed. According to the hardware constraints, the practical range for the switching frequency is selected as [5, 20]kHz, and the DC voltage is chosen as [30, 300]V.

An efficiency map with respect to different DC voltage and switching frequencies is presented in Fig. 5(a), where the efficiency is computed by the DC power from the converter divided by the mechanical power input:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{dc}}{P_m} \tag{16}$$

It is noted that the motor speed and torque are fixed to be 50 RPM and -100 N.m, respectively, which represents a low-power input case in terms of its normal operational range. In addition, from Fig. 5(a) it is seen that the minimum DC voltage is 75 V which is the smallest DC voltage such that the PTO unit is still capable of supplying the required torque (e.g., the FOC control is working properly). This figure presents a clear trend that the efficiency of the PTO unit is higher (maximum around 82%) when both the DC voltage and the switching frequency approach the minimum. This is expected, since smaller switching frequency represents less number of on and off events which leads to less losses. Smaller DC voltage scales down both the conduction loss and switching loss (according to Eq. 11 and 12) which also results in less losses. Moreover, while both the DC voltage and the switching frequency have an impact on the PTO efficiency, the effect of the switching frequency only becomes more visible in high DC voltage. This is because when the DC voltage is higher, the on-off losses are scaled up which represents a significant loss when the number of switches is high.

Figure 5: Efficiency map and losses breakdown with respect to different DC voltage and switching frequency under low-power input condition.

The detailed loss breakdown including the inverter conduction loss, switching loss, and motor conduction loss are presented in Fig. 5(b), 5(c), and 5(d), respectively. It is clearly visible in Fig. 5(c) that the inverter conduction loss is only proportional to the DC voltage. In contrast, the switching loss is impacted by both the DC voltage and switching

frequency. Finally, the conduction loss of the motor nearly has no changes with respect to the DC voltage and the switching frequency. As far as the weights of different losses are concerned, the switching loss is more outstanding compared to the other two, while overall they are at a comparable level of importance.

An efficiency map subject to mid-power input is presented in Fig. 6(a). The motor speed and torque in this case are fixed to be 150 RPM and -500 N.m, respectively. It is apparent in the map that the minimum DC voltage needed to supply the demanded PTO force is much higher (minimum 200 V) than the low-power input case. It is expected that the overall PTO efficiency is lower (maximum 72%) since it needs to support a larger force. With regard to the trend, it is consistent with the low-power input case, where the efficiency is higher when the DC voltage and the switching frequency is smaller. The loss breakdown in mid-power input case is presented in Fig. 6(b), 6(c), and 6(d), respectively. The trend is also consistent with the low-power input case. However, considering the weights of different losses, the conduction losses are more significant than the switching loss since larger voltage and current are induced when supporting a larger force.

Figure 6: Efficiency map and losses breakdown with respect to different DC voltage and switching frequency under mid-power input condition.

3.2 Time Domain Behaviors

In last section, the loss performance of the PTO unit subject to different DC voltage and switching frequencies was analyzed. Further, an opportunity to significantly improve the PTO efficiency by reducing the DC voltage (to the threshold that the PTO still can supply the required control force) and the switching frequency was presented. This opportunity is further discussed via time-domain simulations. Two cases including a small wave and an intermediate wave case are presented and compared. The large wave case is not discussed since the DC voltage has to be utilized to the maximum extend (cannot be optimized).

Figure 7: Mechanical and electrical power production subject to (a) a small wave; (b) an intermediate wave.

The small wave case is first discussed. The regular wave applied in the simulation has a wave height of 0.5m and a period of 6 s. Fig. 7(a) presents the power harvested by the WEC, in which, the blue line represents the mechanical power and the green line denotes the AC power produced (given that the AC power produced under different parameters are nearly the same, only one line is plotted). Furthermore, the black line, maroon line, and red line denote the DC power produced under ($v_{dc} = 300 \text{ V}, F_{sw} = 10 \text{ kHz}$), ($v_{dc} = 300 \text{ V}, F_{sw} = 5 \text{ kHz}$), and ($v_{dc} = 47 \text{ V}, F_{sw} = 5 \text{ kHz}$), respectively. It is clearly visible in the figure that there is a dramatic difference in the DC power harvested under different DC voltage and switching frequency. The DC power produced in these three cases are 105.55 W, 125.33 W, and 164.68 W, respectively. Therefore, the DC power production is improved by 18.74% when only applying the optimal switching frequency, and this improvement is further increased to 56.02% when both the optimal DC voltage and switching frequency are adopted.

Next, the WEC behavior under an intermediate wave is presented. The regular wave applied has a wave height of 1.5 m and a period of 10 s. The WEC power production is presented in Fig. 7(b). The black line, maroon line, and red line denote the DC power produced under ($v_{dc} = 300 \text{ V}, F_{sw} = 10 \text{ kHz}$), ($v_{dc} = 300 \text{ V}, F_{sw} = 5 \text{ kHz}$), and ($v_{dc} = 140 \text{ V}, F_{sw} = 10 \text{ kHz}$), respectively. It is noted that the minimum DC voltage in this case is higher than the small wave case since a larger PTO force needs to be supplied. The harvested DC power are 204.64 W, 279.70 W, and 331.07 W, respectively. Accordingly, in this case, the produced DC power is increased by 36.68% when only the switching frequency is optimal, and the power production is increased by 61.78% when both the optimal DC voltage and switching frequency are applied. Despite the noticeable improvement in terms of the DC power generation, the overall PTO efficiency is decreased in this case which is only around 21.3% in optimal condition compared to 49.94% in the small wave case since the PTO needs to support larger forces.

4. Conclusion

In this research, a high-fidelity wave-to-wire model that considers the detailed dynamic behavior and losses of the switching devices is presented. The parameters of this model are selected such that the numerical model has a good representation of the actual behavior of the hardware. A three-tiered control approach is implemented including the hydrodynamic control, motor control, and the PWM schemes to optimize the wave power production. Varied numerical simulations are conducted to understand the wave-to-wire performance of WECs and the impacts of some key parameters. For instance, it is found the efficiency of the PTO unit is majorly influenced by the DC bus voltage and the switching frequency, and both factors are inversely proportional to the efficiency. By minimizing the DC voltage and the switching frequency to the threshold that the control operates properly, the PTO efficiency can be improved up to 28.52% under constant power input condition. The time domain simulation results further show the DC power production can be improved up to 61.78% when applying the optimal DC voltage and switching frequency. In this paper, it is assumed that the DC voltage is constant during the operational period of the WEC. In future work, the DC voltage will be considered adaptive to further improve the power conversion efficiency. In addition, the proposed concept will be validated in experimental tank tests.

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